

The logo for EVOLVE2CARE features a stylized blue wave above a series of dark blue circles of varying sizes, arranged in a slightly curved line.

EVOLVE2CARE

**D4.1 - Dissemination,
Communication and Outreach
Strategy and Materials**

WP4 - EVOLVE2CARE's People-Centric
Experimentation Ecosystem Outreach,
Sustainability and Clustering

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Reviewer(s)	Marta I. De Los Ríos White [ENoLL]; Francesca Sperandio [ENoLL]		
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List of Abbreviations

D	Deliverable
EC	European Commission
EIT	European Institute of Innovation and Technology
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
KIC	Knowledge and Innovation Community
KoM	Kick-off Meeting
LL	Living Lab(s)
M	Month
MS	Milestone
RTO	Registered Training Organisation
SEO	Search Engine Optimization
T	Task
UC	Use Case
WP	Work Package

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Executive Summary

Deliverable, *D4.1 - Dissemination, Communication, and Outreach Strategy* puts forward a structured framework to maximise the project's impact by sharing its objectives, progress, and outcomes with diverse stakeholders. This strategy is set to assist with the overarching project goals of standardising and enhancing collaboration between Living Labs and HealthTech innovators with a particular focus on the Transitional Care sector.

The strategy is prepared bearing in mind seven fundamental questions:

1. Why to disseminate and communicate?
2. What to disseminate and communicate?
3. Who to disseminate and communicate?
4. How to disseminate and communicate?
5. To Whom to disseminate and communicate?
6. When to disseminate and communicate?
7. Where to disseminate and communicate?

In order to contextualise these questions for the needs and purposes of the present strategy, two ground-setting activities were carried out by the project partners. The 'Product Box' exercise was performed so that partners can brainstorm and collectively outline main information and key points that shall form the basis of all the outreach activities and materials. The 'Assessment of partners outreach resources and capacity' survey was conducted in order to draw better conclusions on the partners' ability (and potential) to contribute to the project's overall dissemination, communication and outreach activities.

Taking stock of the input from the above activities, the strategy elaborates on the creation of a visual identity, the development of digital and print promotional materials, and the management of the project website and social media accounts. It outlines the main target groups and the key messages to feed into the outreach efforts, while it incorporates a phased approach, beginning with awareness-building, transitioning to community engagement, and eventually reaching at global outreach and sustainability.

The strategy is supported by clear action plans, monitoring mechanisms, and predefined Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to ensure measurable impact and alignment with European Commission's (EC) guidelines.

The dissemination level of the deliverable is public, which means that, the intended readership is multifaceted. First and foremost, this deliverable is addressed to the project partners so that they establish a common understanding on dissemination, communication and outreach actions of the project and serve as a guide when needed.

External groups that may be interested in the project's scope, the means that will be utilised to promote the project and its outputs are also part of the target readers. For example, the present strategy can assist in introducing the project to related projects and lead to possible outreach synergies. Last but not least, this deliverable is of relevance to the European Commission (EC) given that it is part of the project's outputs, and the EC is going to evaluate it.

As a cornerstone of the project's outreach efforts, this strategy not only facilitates effective dissemination and communication but also lays the foundation for sustainable exploitation and long-term visibility of EVOLVE2CARE's outcomes, fostering innovation in healthcare through collaboration and stakeholder empowerment. It is essential to annotate that the strategy is perceived as an ongoing effort that is going to be reviewed and updated on a regular basis to assess the achievements and contributions from partners as well as to elaborate on new opportunities, enhanced efforts and even mitigation actions (if needed) that would emerge during the course of the project, thus being agile and relevant to overall progress.

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Introduction

1.1. Project Overview

EVOLVE2CARE focuses on HealthTech experimentation practice to standardise and enhance the collaboration between Living Labs and innovators in the context of the Transitional Care sector. Challenges ranging from aging population to complexity of medical conditions and regulatory frameworks bring a growing recognition of the importance of experimentation practises. By subjecting innovations to real-world environments that involve end-users and stakeholders, EVOLVE2CARE provides innovators with access to services for testing and validating research and products.

The project focuses on three Use Cases (UC): i) Hospital discharge management; ii) Homecare monitoring solutions; and iii) Aging population & care transitions, engaging stakeholders across the whole value chain to examine complexities, barriers and enablers that regulatory framework poses to the development and commercialisation of healthcare innovations.

1.2. WP4 description

Work Package (WP) 4 - EVOLVE2CARE's People-Centric Experimentation Ecosystem Outreach, Sustainability and Clustering, is a horizontal and supporting WP that runs across the entire duration of the project. VIL is the leader of this WP that has the following objectives:

- Raise awareness and maximise the visibility of EVOLVE2CARE achievements among the key target groups.
- Design and develop communication, dissemination and exploitation strategy, activities and materials.
- Disseminate the open call and the various results, reports, and findings generated by the project.
- Publicise the trainings, webinars, and other online public activities.
- Plan and verify the potential of all exploitable outcomes during and after project's end.
- Build and engage a community of stakeholders around EVOLVE2CARE.
- Establish synergies with relevant clusters, projects and initiatives.
- Co-design exploitation plans and sustainable business models for the project results and a market and business plan for the project's main tangible outcome.

In order to meet the above-listed objectives WP4 consists of three tasks:

*Table 1. WP4 objectives distribution within Tasks**

WP4 Tasks	Obj.1	Obj.2	Obj.3	Obj.4	Obj.5	Obj.6	Obj.7	Obj.8
T4.1 EVOLVE2CARE Dissemination, Communication and Outreach for the Open Calls								
T4.2 Exploitation and IPR of AccelUP								
T4.3 Clustering with EIT KICs								

* Green cells indicate primary contribution, and light green cells indicate complementary contribution

1.3. Purpose and scope of the deliverable

D4.1 - Dissemination, Communication and Outreach Strategy and Materials puts forward the strategy addressing the measures and activities for project’s dissemination, communication and overall outreach efforts. It elaborates on the project’s objectives, key messages and their respective target audiences. It presents the visual identity of the project, the corresponding digital and print materials to be designed and the means to be leveraged both online and onsite to cover every fundamental aspect of the dissemination, communication and outreach goals. It also outlines the planning and monitoring procedures to ensure the quality and the effectiveness of such activities.

This strategy is a cornerstone of WP4. It is considered an ongoing effort that is going to be reviewed and updated on a regular basis to assess the achievements and contributions from partners as well as to elaborate on new opportunities, enhanced efforts and even mitigation actions (if needed) that would emerge during the course of the project, thus being agile and relevant to overall progress.

1.4. Structure

The present deliverable is structured to provide a comprehensive and logical overview of the Dissemination, Communication, and Outreach Strategy for the EVOLVE2CARE project. The document is organised into the following sections:

- **Introduction:** This section outlines the project’s background, objectives, and the purpose of the deliverable. It also includes an overview of WP4, which is dedicated to outreach, sustainability, and clustering activities, emphasising its importance in achieving the project’s goals.

- **The Strategy:** The main body of the deliverable presents the strategy in detail, starting with the European Commission’s obligations and definitions of dissemination, communication, and exploitation. It introduces the methodology used, including the 7Ws approach and the Product Box exercise, to ensure a structured and inclusive planning process. Subsections elaborate on the scope and objectives, target audiences, key messages, tools, channels, and networks to be utilised.
- **Monitoring and Evaluation:** This section describes the governance structure followed for the implementation of this strategy and mechanisms for tracking and assessing the effectiveness of dissemination and communication efforts. It includes the action plan with defined phases and timelines, as well as reporting and feedback procedures to ensure continuous improvement and alignment with project objectives.
- **Conclusions:** The document concludes with a summary of the strategy’s achievements, emphasising its role in promoting the project’s impact, sustainability, and long-term value to the HealthTech and Transitional Care sector.
- **Annex:** Supporting materials such as templates for dissemination reporting, stakeholder mapping, and activity planning are included in the annex to provide practical tools for implementation.

2. The strategy

The purpose of the *D4.1 – Dissemination, Communication and Outreach Strategy and Materials* is to establish a comprehensive framework and guidelines for the effective implementation of all the dissemination, communication and outreach activities. It, also, seeks to ensure that such actions are in line with the project's overarching goals and the interlinked objectives from other project WPs.

The strategy draws from and gives right back to all the WPs of the project, which means that the project partners are requested to align all their dissemination, communication and overall outreach actions consulting this strategy.

2.1. European Commission's obligations and definitions

Prior to unfolding the actual strategy, it is essential to pay attention to the European Commission's guidelines regarding the legal obligation for beneficiaries of Horizon Europe funding schemes to carry out activities to increase the impact of the project results¹ through:

- **Dissemination:** *Sharing research results with people who can best make use of them, such as the scientific community, industry, commercial players, civil society and policymakers relevant to the project's scope.*

Provided that the European Union's (EU) grants are financed by public funds, beneficiaries are expected to actively engage in communication activities and to promote the projects too, through:

- **Communication:** *Taking strategic and targeted measures for promoting the action itself and its results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public, and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange.*

What is more, the EC indicates that impact maximisation, also, has to derive from:

- **Exploitation:** *Using the project's results in developing, creating and marketing or improving a product, process, or service, or shaping a policy that could have a positive impact on the public's quality of life.*

¹"Dissemination and exploitation - European Commission," [rea.ec.europa.eu](https://rea.ec.europa.eu/dissemination-and-exploitation_en).
https://rea.ec.europa.eu/dissemination-and-exploitation_en

2.2. Methodology

2.2.1. The 7Ws approach

Bearing in mind the EC operationalised terms, the dissemination, communication and outreach strategy is drafted so that it can address seven basic questions, whose origin can be traced back to the five W's principle often mentioned in journalism, research and police investigation, and they constitute a formula for getting the complete story of a subject.² The present strategy opts for an extended version that is, the 7Ws approach, whose purpose is to navigate the preparation of the strategy making sure that all essential parts can be covered. The 7W's are outlined as following:

Table 2. The 7 W's approach to dissemination and communication

Dissemination and communication questions	Explanation
Why to disseminate and communicate?	The dissemination and communication efforts address multiple purposes. First, they fulfil the contractual obligations of the consortium. Additionally, such efforts aim to showcase the work delivered by the project partners throughout the implementation of the project and foster the transfer of the project's results to subsequent initiatives. They also afford getting stakeholders on board with project actions. Last but not least they pave the way for future exploitation actions , ensuring the long-term sustainability of the project's outcomes.
What to disseminate and communicate?	The information to be shared revolves around multiple aspects of the project including project achievements, highlighting completed tasks, milestones, project events (such as workshops, training sessions, calls to action, final conference etc.). The information can also refer to project results , such as public deliverables, data, scientific and /or technical knowledge, good practices, and applied methodologies that contribute to the implementation and delivery of the project outcomes. Furthermore, lessons learned can be shared as valuable insights for third parties.

² Adobe Communications Team, "5 Ws (and 1 H) To Be Asked of Every Project | Adobe Workfront," *Adobe.com*, 2018. [https://business.adobe.com/blog/basics/project-management-101-the-5-
ws-and-1-h-that-should-be-asked-of-every-project](https://business.adobe.com/blog/basics/project-management-101-the-5-ws-and-1-h-that-should-be-asked-of-every-project)

Who to disseminate and communicate?	All project partners are assigned with carrying out dissemination and communication activities, taking on either leading roles and/or contributing collectively.
How to disseminate and communicate?	A variety of tools, channels, and networks can be utilised to effectively convey the messages of the project. These include the project's website, newsletter issues, social media accounts, publications in peer-reviewed journals, conference papers, articles and interviews in mass media, press releases, face-to-face meetings with stakeholders and target groups, participation in third-party events such as conferences, workshops, EC events, and exhibitions. Additionally, promotional materials can be drafted to communicate information about the project.
To Whom to disseminate and communicate?	The target audience includes the stakeholders from diverse fields who can be interested and/or even positively impacted by the project's outcomes . Such audiences can represent academia and the research community, public sector, private stakeholders from business and industry sectors, and civil society.
When to disseminate and communicate?	The implementation of dissemination and communication activities lasts throughout the duration of the project. It may even go beyond its completion when this stated on the contractual obligations and/or it is linked to the rights and responsibilities for the exploitation of results.
Where to disseminate and communicate?	Given the multifaceted nature of the dissemination and communication efforts, the activities can be carried out in diverse settings including online/digital, hybrid and physical/on-site environments.

2.2.2. Product Box exercise

In order to contextualise the 7Ws approach to the EVOLVE2CARE project case and provide a foundation for the present strategy, the project partners have undertaken a ground-setting, brainstorming activity, titled 'Product Box' exercise. The activity was presented by VIL, the WP4 leader, during the first day of the project's Kick-off Meeting (KoM), Thursday 30 October 2024.

In agile software development the product box activity outlines how a product is developed. It helps explaining the solutions of a component the same way a marketer could describe a product's features and unique selling points on its packaging³. In the context of the EVOLVE2CARE, the goal has been to share ideas, pick up each other's minds and eventually co-design the main information and key points that shall form the

³ M. Iqbal, "The Product Box; An Agile Planning," *Mudassir Iqbal*, Aug. 25, 2023. <https://mudassiriqbal.net/the-product-box-an-agile-planning/>

basis of all the outreach activities and materials (i.e., website, project videos, leaflets, open calls, etc.).

Following this concept the consortium examined a set of questions distributed to the different parts of the ‘product box’ (see Figure 1). The parts of the box featured the following key points and their respective, descriptive questions:

- **Value proposition:** *What is the EVOLVE2CARE project? What is the novelty that it brings? What are the benefits of using it?*
- **How it works?** *How can someone make use of the project? Are there any specific steps to be followed or any kind of criteria to be covered?*
- **Target groups:** *Who is EVOVLE2CARE for?*
- **Needs met:** *Is there any gap that EVOVLE2CARE covers, or any 'customer pain relief' that offers?*
- **Slogan(s):** *Can we summarise our value proposition in a couple messages? Can we fit our project goal in a few catch-phrases?*
- **End-goal(s):** *What do we really aim for by the end of the project? Which outcomes do we really want to sustain and uptake further?*

Figure 1. EVOLVE2CARE ‘Product Box’ exercise concept

The afore-listed points guided an open-ended session during the WP4’s part in the project KoM. The exercise remained active for the follow up week in order to let all partners the time to elaborate on their feedback further and share additional information. The consolidated input has been integrated into the present strategy (see Section 2.3), thus rendering it a participatory effort and fostering a deeper sense of

ownership of the dissemination, communication and outreach efforts by all partners early in the project.

2.2.3. Assessment of partners outreach resources and capacity

In addition to the Product Box exercise, an internal assessment has been conducted to map the partners outreach resources and capacity. The rationale of this complementary action has been to draw better conclusions on the partners’ ability (and potential) to contribute to the project’s overall dissemination, communication and outreach activities.

The assessment has been drafted by VIL and run using the EUSurvey platform. Each partner was asked to fill in a brief questionnaire regarding what resources are being utilised by each organisation for their outreach purposes/needs; what connections are established in each partner networks that could be valuable for the project’s awareness raising and engaging goals; and how each partner could contribute to disseminating the EVOLVE2CARE project scope and results.

The table below summarises the most significant findings:

Table 3. Summarised findings from the partners’ outreach resources and capacity assessment

Assessment questions	Key points														
Online Channels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ In addition to their official websites, all partners stated having a dedicated intranet, as well as a calendar/online agenda where news and events are communicated within the organisation. 														
Newsletters	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ ENoLL and SPLORO issue their own newsletters. 														
Other digital or print publications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ AUTH and ENoLL also publish (and will publish) digital magazines during the duration of the project. 														
Social Media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ LinkedIn is used by all five partners, whilst Facebook and Instagram are also more active platforms for some partners. <table border="1"> <caption>Social Media Usage</caption> <thead> <tr> <th>Platform</th> <th>Count</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Facebook</td> <td>4</td> </tr> <tr> <td>X (Twitter)</td> <td>2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>LinkedIn</td> <td>5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Instagram</td> <td>3</td> </tr> <tr> <td>YouTube</td> <td>1</td> </tr> <tr> <td>TikTok</td> <td>1</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Platform	Count	Facebook	4	X (Twitter)	2	LinkedIn	5	Instagram	3	YouTube	1	TikTok	1
	Platform	Count													
Facebook	4														
X (Twitter)	2														
LinkedIn	5														
Instagram	3														
YouTube	1														
TikTok	1														
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ All partners are very active in sharing news about their projects in their social media, since they either post in a weekly or a monthly basis. <table border="1"> <caption>Posting Frequency</caption> <thead> <tr> <th>Frequency</th> <th>Count</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Frequently (e.g. every month)</td> <td>2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Super frequently! (e.g. every week)</td> <td>3</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Frequency	Count	Frequently (e.g. every month)	2	Super frequently! (e.g. every week)	3								
Frequency	Count														
Frequently (e.g. every month)	2														
Super frequently! (e.g. every week)	3														

Assigned person	✓ Three out of five partners employ a specific person to handle their communication activities (i.e., communications officer, PR account manager, etc.).
Networks	✓ All partners point out being members of wider networks that can be relevant to the project’s scope.
Own events	✓ AUTH and ENOLL host their own events whose topics can be relevant to the project’s scope.
Third party events	✓ The partners have expressed their plans to leverage noteworthy call to actions from the scientific community and disseminate the project in identified forthcoming events.
Scientific and/or technical peer-reviewed publications	✓ AUTH and VIL indicated that they are interested in pursuing opportunities to publish scientific papers.

Taking into account the aforementioned preparatory actions and the input collected from partners, the present strategy is structured in the following five main parts:

1. **Scope and objectives**
2. **Target audiences**
3. **Key messages**
4. **Tools, channels and networks**
5. **Monitoring and evaluation**

2.3. Scope and objectives

The dissemination, communication and outreach strategy in the EVOLVE2CARE project is going to play the following fundamental roles:

1. raise awareness about the project;
2. convey adequate information in timely manner and via the right means;
3. engage with the target audiences to maximise the reach of the project’s activities and results; thereby
4. contribute to successful implementation, viable sustainability and future exploitation of the project’s key outcomes.

Based on the above, the envisioned efforts should be aligned with the main goal of the project to standardise and enhance the collaboration between Living Labs and innovators in the context of healthcare, with a particular focus on the Transitional Care sector. Hence, the main objective to steer the present strategy can be elaborated on the following lines:

Disseminating and communicating the project will seek to bring innovators, researchers, regulators, and other HealthTech stakeholders closer to Living Labs inside an ecosystem that fosters experimentation and eventually provides a novel market-centric paradigm for collaboration that breaks down silos.

Moreover, the present strategy also identifies additional project objectives, that can be interlinked with the envisioned dissemination, communication and outreach efforts:

The project will put forward a scouting and selection process for innovators across EU to benefit from Health and Wellbeing Living Labs, certified by the [Accelup Platform](#), a product of ENoLL developed under the Vitalise project⁴ that provides an online space for wider, simplified, and more efficient access to the certified Living Lab infrastructures and their research on demand services. Therefore, it is of great relevance to the present strategy to bring this project action into the spotlight, explain it to diverse audiences and create traffic/visibility for the Accelup platform along with the actual project.

This sub-objective also expands to onboarding new Living Labs from the Healthcare sector into the Accelup, while promoting to target stakeholders how the project leverages the added value of the platform and how this is distinguishable from other similar initiatives and/or endeavours. The end-goal is to showcase the EVOLVE2CARE as a best practice case for the Accelup platform.

Furthermore, it is a core value within the project's ambition to create strategies for effective knowledge sharing among legal, regulatory, fiscal, and operational entities about complexities and drivers for testing of HealthTech innovations in Transitional Care. In this sense, the project will seek to impact decision-making communities via its produced knowledge and lessons learnt, that should lay the foundation for harmonisation of experimentation and support services in the Transitional Care sector. Dissemination efforts of the project are going to also gravitate towards this sub-objective.

⁴ "Home," *Vitalise-project.eu*, 2023. <https://vitalise-project.eu/> (accessed Dec. 30, 2024).

The Vitalise project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101007990

Figure 2. Overview of the dissemination, communication and outreach objectives

2.3.1. Target audiences

Drawing from the Product Box exercise, the pool of targeted audiences that will form the EVOLVE2CARE stakeholders' community has been primarily identified and is going to comprise stakeholders that can impact and can be impacted by the project's efforts and outcomes. Such audiences can be enlisted according to the following classification:

Table 4. Target audiences' classification

Target audiences	Brief description, benefits and related impact
Innovators	<p>Who belong(s) in this target group? This group represents startups, SMEs corporates, and researchers focused on HealthTech solutions. They provide insights into the technological, operational, and market-oriented challenges and opportunities for innovation in the project's case study field.</p>
	<p>What can they obtain by engaging with the project? They will receive personalised matching with Living Labs based on their goals, expertise and interests; and make informed decisions based on the resources each Living Lab can offer. They will be able to accelerate their experimentation process thanks to efficient partnerships. They shall increase their own visibility; and get guidance on creating pitches, presentations, business plans to attract investors.</p>
Accelerators and Investors	<p>Who belong(s) in this target group? Organisations and individuals providing funding and mentorship to innovative projects comprise this group. Their feedback can be valuable focusing on funding gaps, market dynamics, and investment priorities.</p>
	<p>What can they obtain by engaging with the project?</p>

	<p>They will be able to observe how innovations function in real-life environments, while also engaging in the innovation process by sharing best practices, knowledge bases and resources. They will be able to explore new collaborations and draw better conclusions influenced by positive or negative experimentation outcomes.</p>
<p>Living Labs</p>	<p>Who belong(s) in this target group? This group consists of Living Labs certified by ENOLL, specifically active on Health and Wellbeing, who contribute perspectives on the practicalities of real-world experimentation, including resource allocation and stakeholder engagement.</p>
	<p>What can they obtain by engaging with the project? The onboarded Living Labs will have the opportunity to connect with stakeholders, thus growing their brand name and their portfolio of services and opening up the market for new high-tech HealthTech products and services. These Living Labs will be able to eventually increase revenue through a market-centric framework.</p>
<p>End-users (Care Units, Hospitals, Practitioners)</p>	<p>Who belong(s) in this target group? This group includes hospital administrators, clinicians, and healthcare professionals who provide valuable insights into the practical deployment and adoption of innovative solutions within healthcare systems.</p>
	<p>What can they obtain by engaging with the project? They are the recipients of HealthTech innovations emerging from real-life experimentation processes involving innovators and Living Labs. These advancements will enhance their work by providing cutting-edge tools and solutions to address healthcare challenges. They will have the opportunity to evaluate these innovative solutions and provide valuable feedback, guiding the experimentation towards a more responsive, resilient, and patient-centred healthcare future.</p>
<p>End-users (Individuals)</p>	<p>Who belong(s) in this target group? Patients and caregivers (informal or formal) who experience the challenges of transitional care firsthand are included in this group. They can contribute personal insights on usability, accessibility, and the real-world impact of innovation in the Transitional Care sector.</p>
	<p>What can they obtain by engaging with the project? Individuals such as patients and caregivers can benefit from improved care processes, enhanced support systems, and innovative solutions that address their specific needs. They will also have the opportunity to influence the development of these solutions through their feedback, ensuring that the outcomes are both user-friendly and impactful in real-world settings.</p>

Policymakers and Regulatory Bodies	<p>Who belong(s) in this target group? This group entails policymakers and representatives from regulatory bodies whose perspectives on legislative and compliance challenges affecting HealthTech solutions are integral.</p>
	<p>What can they obtain by engaging with the project? They can assess, recognise and support transformative innovation by utilising Living Labs real-life experimentation approach and collective knowledge on research agendas. Empirical data stemming from the project can be a valuable resource for evidence-based policymaking contributing to the current understanding and future formulations of HealthTech regulations.</p>
EU Initiatives	<p>Who belong(s) in this target group? This group is formed from representatives from EU-funded projects and initiatives, including EIT Health, that can share insights on leveraging existing networks and frameworks to foster innovation.</p>
	<p>What can they obtain by engaging with the project? Collaboration opportunities in the area of innovation testing is a valuable asset for this group. This group can benefit from networking and coordination structures, as well as tools that facilitate innovation development. These include access to and the sharing of best practices, resources, talent, markets, expertise, services, and knowledge—such as open and collaborative knowledge bases and common knowledge assets (e.g., methods, data, and processes).</p>

The above classification of target groups is valuable not only for outreach efforts but for the overall project’s implementation as well. Multiple tasks across the project will have to engage with such groups to fulfil their objectives. Hence, the present strategy is going to dive deeper into the mapping of stakeholders in parallel with ongoing tasks as the collective efforts proceed.

The mapping of stakeholders is going to be one of the primary actions taken in the context of dissemination, communication and outreach planning in the forthcoming period. Likewise, the assessment of partners’ outreach resources, a succinct exercise is going to be done in order to create an initial database of stakeholders that can be interested and/or purposeful for the EVOLVE2CARE actions. The timeframe for this exercise shall be set for the first six months of the project, that is from October 2025 to March 2025. The templates of the exercise are listed in the Annex.

2.3.2. Key messages

The messages to be disseminated and/or communicated need to entail the project’s vision in a pertinent and comprehensive way, highlighting the EVOLVE2CARE’s key function in the field of Transitional Care.

The content should be crafted in a non-discriminatory language, which means that information should be characterised **by inclusive and context-sensitive terms**. The use of plural number should be preferred in most cases (see Table 5); while reviewing the content of tailored messages towards target groups such as the patients and caregivers (end-users) should be opted among partners to ensure that the project engages with its audiences appropriately. All partners should consult with VIL, the WP4 Leader and AUTH, the project coordinator, when creating their outreach messages and materials.

Bearing in mind the above, a few tentative key messages of the project’s outreach strategy, as those have also stemmed from the Product Box exercise revolve around the following points:

Table 5. Tentative key messages for different target audiences

Target audience	Key message(s)
Innovators	<p>Drive innovation in healthcare: Join us to access Living Labs and fast-track your HealthTech solutions in real-world settings.</p> <p>Expand your impact: Gain visibility, build strategic partnerships, and receive guidance to attract investors.</p> <p>Shape the future: Co-create cutting-edge solutions to revolutionise the Transitional Care sector.</p>
Accelerators and Investors	<p>Support transformative ideas: Witness the impact of HealthTech innovations in real-life experiments.</p> <p>Strategic insights: Identify funding gaps and investment opportunities in a growing market.</p> <p>Collaborate to innovate: Partner with key stakeholders to influence and validate high-impact innovations.</p>
Living Labs	<p>Expand your reach: Connect with innovators and diversify your services to include HealthTech advancements.</p> <p>Real-world validation: Play a pivotal role in testing and scaling innovations for the Transitional Care sector.</p> <p>Market-driven growth: Unlock new revenue streams through collaborative experimentation.</p>
End-users (Care Units, Hospitals, Practitioners)	<p>Enhance patient care: Adopt state-of-the-art HealthTech solutions tailored to real healthcare needs.</p> <p>Be a changemaker: Provide critical feedback to shape innovations that support a resilient, patient-centered healthcare system.</p>

	Streamline workflows: Experience the benefits of technology that addresses everyday challenges in care delivery.
End-users (Individuals)	Better care, better lives: Benefit from improved processes and personalised HealthTech solutions. Your voice matters: Share your experiences to influence the development of user-friendly innovations. HealthTech that listens: Discover solutions designed with your needs at the focus.
Policymakers and Regulatory Bodies	Evidence-based impact: Utilise insights from real-world experiments to inform future healthcare policies. Accelerate innovation: Support HealthTech advancements by leveraging project outcomes and collective expertise. Shape the framework: Lead the way in creating policies that enable transformative healthcare solutions.
EU Initiatives	Leverage synergies: Collaborate with EVOLVE2CARE to integrate innovation networks and frameworks. Access shared resources: Benefit from best practices, knowledge assets, and collaborative tools. Strengthen the ecosystem: Build partnerships to drive innovation across the HealthTech landscape.

It is essential to understand that the messages the project will convey are subject to many iterations as the project progresses. Being agile and able to depict the concurrent status of the project is integral to the elaboration of the key messages. In this respect, the messages are going to be based on the produced knowledge during the different phases of the project and reflect important moments and achievements through its lifecycle, such as milestones, deliverables and open calls for contributions.

2.4. Tools, channels and networks

Having set the foundations in the previous sub-chapters, the next important aspect to be addressed is the utilisation of appropriate tools, channels and networks. The paragraphs below elaborate on all the necessary means to carry out effective and adequate dissemination, communication and outreach activities in accordance with the EC guidelines and the strategy's scope.

2.4.1. Visual Identity

Starting from the project's visual identity, it consists of visual and textual cues that render the project branding recognisable, reflective of its vision and versatile.

2.4.1.1. Logo

The EVOLVE2CARE logo acts as the project's first connection with the audiences, and it is considered the cornerstone of a coherent visual identity to trademark the partners' work in any electronic and/or print outputs.

Figure 3. EVOLVE2CARE logo

The logo consists of the project emblem and the official acronym. The use of the full project's title '*Engaging the Value of Living Labs to Innovate Care and Regulatory Environments*' is going to be opted for formats and layouts that can afford sufficient space to be featured, for example, the project website, presentations, posters, project public documents and media outputs like newsletters.

2.4.1.2. Colour Scheme

The colour scheme of the project logo, along with the complementary colours, is the following:

- Primary Colour: #366087 [Lapis Lazuli]
- Secondary Colour 1: # 65A5D3 [Air Superiority Blue]
- Secondary Colour 2: # 95D3EA [Sky Blue]
- Secondary Colour 3: #E2FDFF [Light Cyan]
- Extra Colour 1: #57C3A6 [Mint]
- Extra Colour 2: #C5DCA0 [Tea Green]

Figure 4. EVOLVE2CARE colour scheme

The selection of the colours has been assessed so that it remains distinguishable and clear for people who might experience accessibility issues both in digital and print formats.

The project's [Brand Book](#) provides a comprehensive set of information and guidelines about the project's visual identity and its properties.

2.4.2. Materials

2.4.2.1. Templates

Drawing from the project logo and colour scheme, a set of templates have been drafted based on the above-presented features. A great volume of deliverables, presentations and reports produced by project partners is going to be disseminated, so defined templates for text documents, and presentations are prepared ensuring professional diligence, correct use of the project branding and compliance with EU's guidelines to all the project's documents and communications.

Moreover, **both text documents and presentation templates entail important instructions for project partners regarding the correct use of the project's visual features and guidelines for adequate acknowledgement of EU funding.** These templates are necessary and provide the partners a better look and feel so that they can deliver their various reports in a uniformed way.

EVOLVE2CARE
DX.X - Deliverable title
WPX - Title
Month 202X | Version 1.X

Text Format	Configurations				
	Font	Size	Style	Colour	Alignment
Heading 1	Poppins	24	Normal	#366088	Justified
Heading 2	Poppins	18	Normal	#366088	Justified
Heading 3	Poppins	14	Normal	#366088	Justified
Normal Text	Open Sans	12	Normal	#000000	Justified
Captions	Open Sans	11	Italics	#366088	Centered

Table 1. Text formats and configurations

2. Main Part
Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Phasellus tempus quis lorem sed lacinia. Mauris quis euismod sapien, sed mollis sapien.

2.1. Text formatting
Project documents' fonts:

- Poppins (for Headings and titles)
- Open Sans (for normal text, subtitles and captions)

2.2. Funding Acknowledgement
The EU funding should always be declared in uniformed and straightforward fashion:

- The plain format is simply adding the default logo
 - It should be used for printed and digital materials alike including brochures, banners, posters, flyers, videos, newsletters, press releases, agendas, participants lists and any other outputs to be created in the context of (and for) the project's outreach activities.
- The complete format consists of the default logo + the funding acknowledgement statement that must be added as follows:
 - "This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101158152."
 - The complete funding must be used for all the project's deliverables, reporting documents to be handed to the EC, the project website and any secondary web application to be set up to support project's implementation, and scientific papers.

Figure 5. EVOLVE2CARE deliverable template - snapshot

2.4.2.2. Online meetings background

Given the frequency of virtual meetings that should be expected throughout the project's duration, as well as online trainings and participation in external events, it is recommended that a project-relevant background image is used by partners whenever they are going to represent the project in events of digital format. The background image is drafted following the essential colours of the scheme presented above; and its usage is optional to the partners, albeit highly encouraged.

Figure 6. EVOLVE2CARE online meetings background image

2.4.2.3. Preliminary promotional slides

In addition to the project's templates, an important volume of promotional materials is going to be delivered within the project to meet the purposes/needs of the dissemination, communication and outreach efforts. Such materials will be of diverse formats and layouts, accommodating both digital and printed versions. The role of promotional materials is going to be essential to the needs of the present strategy, as the project recognises the versatile applications of materials like, flyers and leaflets, cards, slideshows, short videos, banners and posters for multiple kinds of instances.

Drawing from the project templates and the guidelines for proper use of the visual identity, VIL has already collaborated with partners to draft the preliminary promotional slides, thus setting the tone for the creation of the project's materials. The delivery of these initial promotional slides has established the preferences for the materials creation and prompt the first AUTH efforts to introduce the project to target groups and raise awareness for the upcoming project actions.

The promotional slides are presented below:

COMING SOON

EVOLVE2CARE

Engaging the Value Of Living Labs to Innovate Care And Regulatory Environments

Key Info

- Duration: 24 Months
- EC Funding: € 987 230,14
- Type: Coordination & Support Action
- Consortium: 5 Project Partners

Project coordination

Laboratory of Medical Physics & Digital Innovation
Aristotle University of Thessaloniki

Funded by the European Union

COMING SOON

Open Calls

EVOLVE2CARE is going to **bring together certified Living Labs with innovators** to experiment and validate research outcomes **for the Transitional Care sector**

Three use cases to explore HealthTech solutions

- Homecare Monitoring Solutions
- Hospital Discharge Management
- Ageing Population & Care Transitions

COMING SOON

Recruitment Process

Living Labs ↔ **ccelup** Find your innovation partner ↔ Innovators

European Network of Living Labs

Eligibility Check → Evaluation → Matching & Onboarding → Execution

Key Info

- Duration: 24 Months
- EC Funding: € 987 230,14
- Type: Coordination & Support Action
- Consortium: 5 Project Partners

Project coordination

Laboratory of Medical Physics & Digital Innovation
Aristotle University of Thessaloniki

Funded by the European Union

Figure 7. EVOLVE2CARE preliminary promotional slides

2.4.2.4. Preliminary flyer

Following the promotional slides first draft, a preliminary version of an EVOLVE2CARE flyer has also been created. VIL has worked in conjunction with ENoLL to have the first version of the project flyer ready to be shared during the COHEHERE 2024 Conference

in Ghent, Belgium. The event organised by COHEHRE Association⁵ was hosted by the Odisee University of Applied Sciences and the Artevelde University of Applied Sciences, for three days (18-20 of November) and elaborated on the theme of *“Revolutionising Health Education: The impact of Innovative Practice”*. Partners from AUTH coordination and ENoLL team took part in the conference to promote the project’s kick-off and distributed the flyers to the attendees.

The flyer, which is presented below, is going to be periodically revised to produce updated versions. Moreover, this flyer’s layout is going to be leveraged as a template for the preparation of additional materials such as posters/banners and project’s business cards.

⁵ “COHEHRE | Consortium of Institutes of Higher Education in Health and Rehabilitation in Europe,” *Coehre.com*, 2024. <https://www.coehre.com/> (accessed Dec. 30, 2024).

Figure 8. EVOLVE2CARE preliminary flyer (front and back)

2.4.3. Online Channels

2.4.3.1. Website

The project's website has been officially launched in October 2024 (M1), under the domain name <https://evolve2care.eu/>. The major function of the website is to share the project's progress and outcomes with all the target stakeholders and general audiences. It features the necessary information regarding the actual project, news about the project, materials and resources.

The website's layout is aligned with the characteristics of the project's visual identity, including the colour scheme and the typography, while the overall style matches the promotional materials to maintain a uniformed and coherent appearance.

Figure 9. EVOLVE2CARE website homepage

Figure 10. EVOLVE2CARE website homepage – Project Partners

Figure 11. EVOLVE2CARE website homepage – News & Updates

The launched website entails a landing page, as shown in the above figures, an about section where essential information about the project, such as the project’s vision, methodology and composition, are available; a news and updates section; a contact page and a preliminary page dedicated to the open calls that the project is going to organise in order to bring innovators of HealthTech into collaboration with certified Living Labs.

In-order to be ‘user-friendly’, a search engine functionality has been added within the website, which allows users to search any content within the website. Moreover, the website is Search Engine Optimization (SEO) friendly, and basic SEO practices have been applied (i.e., fixing of the meta elements, keywords, optimization for performance).

Figure 12. EVOLVE2CARE website – Open Calls

The next steps for the project’s website set up will focus on publishing more sections that will feature further key information. Namely, the about section is going to be enhanced with details about each partner’s role in the project and the composition of their teams; a new page is going to be dedicated to the project’s Advisory Board (AB) members; and a resources page is going to be created to aggregate public deliverables upon their admission by the EC, relevant presentations and publications conducted by partners, communication materials (i.e., blog posts, videos, infographics, posters, newsletters and press releases). Moreover, the open calls section is going to be updated with more details and instructions for the interested third parties as the project matures its preparations for this major activity.

The figure below depicts the tentative sitemap that is going to be the basis of the website set up next steps in the forthcoming months. Timewise, this process is set to be concluded by the end of the first semester of the project, that is March 2025 (M6):

Figure 13. EVOLVE2CARE website – tentative sitemap

VIL is the responsible partner for the maintenance and update of the EVOLVE2CARE website, with support from AUTH, since the website is hosted at the main server of the

coordinator's infrastructure. Its performance will be monitored on a monthly basis via the Google Analytics in order to keep track of the traffic and the visitors' engagement.

Last but not least, VIL is going to consult with partners, especially with AUTH, to install appropriate widgets that will ensure the accessibility of the website for diverse audiences.

2.4.3.2. Social Media Pages

Along with the project's site, the EVOLVE2CARE social media pages were set up in October 2024 (M1), since such online channels play an essential role for sharing messages and communicating with target audiences in almost real time. The project's strategy has opted to utilise **Facebook and LinkedIn platforms**. The maintenance of these pages is led by VIL, while all partners are going to be responsible to provide contents that would possibly be of interest for the target groups.

In addition and based on the input from the outreach capacity assessment, partners are **strongly encouraged to react and share the project's social media posts via their organisation's social media accounts**. Tagging the accounts indicated by the partners surveys is going to be utilised so that wide spreading the content of the EVOLVE2CARE social media posts can take place seamlessly from partners' organisations side. Tagging personal accounts of the partners team members that they take part in activities which are going to be posted in the project's social media, is optional and VIL, as social media manager, is going to request permission from these persons ad hoc.

Having vivid and engaging pages shall require frequent posting with an adequate quality resembling the project's visual identity. To this end the content is going to feature multiple information, which can be mainly consist of (but not limited to) the following project's parts:

- Outreach activities (e.g., workshops, demonstrations, webinars, meetings with stakeholders, and more) organised by the project;
- Participations and contributions to third party events and conferences;
- Project promotional materials (e.g., infographics, project cards, videos, posters, etc.);
- Blog posts featuring insights from EVOLVE2CARE public deliverables;
- Press releases and newsletter of the project;
- EVOLVE2CARE publications (including available links);
- Synergy activities with other similar EU funded projects and initiatives;
- Updates from project meetings.

Specific hashtags (#) to highlight key elements of EVOLVE2CARE will always accompany the project's posts to motivate the targeted, interested stakeholders and the general

public to be informed about the project’s latest activities and news. An indicative list of relevant hashtags for the project’s social media posts is provided below, while other hashtags might be used according to the needs:

Table 6. List of indicative hashtags

Indicative hashtags	
#HorizonEurope	#Innovation
#HorizonEU	# Research
#Healthcare	#Development
#HealthTech	#Experimentation
#TransitionalCare	#LivingLabs
#PatientCare	#Accelup
#SmartHealthcare	#CoCreation
#DigitalHealth	#Community
#eHealth	#CitizenScience
#RemoteCare	#Market
#Recovery	#Product
#Caregiver	#Service
#HealthData	#Business
#HealthEquity	#EndUsers
#Wellbeing	#OpenCall
#Wellness	#Voucher

Facebook Page

The Facebook page of the project is titled [Evolve2Care](#). The category of the pages is set as ‘Medical lab · Science and tech’, while the Bio entails the following message: “A two-year Horizon Europe project (Grant Agreement No: 101158152) that brings together Living Labs and Health Tech innovators in the context of the Transitional Care sector”.

Figure 14. EVOLVE2CARE Facebook page

Figure 15. EVOLVE2CARE Facebook page - posts

LinkedIn page

The LinkedIn page of the project is titled [EVOLVE2CARE HorizonEU](#). The category of the page is set as 'Research services', while the Overview of the page entails the following message: *"Funded by the European Union (Grant Number: 101158152) EVOLVE2CARE project brings together Living Labs and Health Tech innovators in the context of the Transitional Care sector. The project will provide innovators with access to services for testing and validating research and products."*

Figure 16. EVOVLE2CARE LinkedIn page

Figure 17. EVOLVE2CARE LinkedIn page – post

Bearing in mind that the first months of the project gravitate towards preparatory efforts, the audience count of both Facebook and LinkedIn pages is going to be boosted once the project has established the very first ties with its stakeholders' community and the relevant mapping (see reference to sub-section 2.3.1.) is carried out. What is more, intra-institutional awareness regarding the project is going to be sought by project partners leveraging the preliminary promotional materials.

YouTube channel

In order to facilitate the promotion of audiovisual content, such as video animations, reels, interviews and campaign videos that will advertise the project on diverse occasions, a YouTube channel was also created in October 2024 (M1). The set up followed the above-described procedures for social media pages. The channel is named

[EVOLVE2CARE Project HorizonEU](#) and is going to feature all the audiovisual materials to be drafted in the context of the dissemination, communication and outreach activities for the project. In this respect, the preliminary animated video of the project was created by VIL in December 2024 (M3) and uploaded to the YouTube channel. It is a brief overview of the project's scope and fundamental information.

Figure 18. EVOLVE2CARE preliminary animated video

2.4.3.3. Newsletter

EVOLVE2CARE is planning to publish regular newsletters as the project unfolds to communicate its progress and outcomes, as well as next steps towards multiple target groups. In order to meet such needs, an account has been created on the Mailchimp platform. The rationale for this choice is that being one of the most utilised and trusted platforms for newsletter services, Mailchimp prioritises privacy and complies with GDPR regulations. Also, the platform ensures smooth embedding with other online channels. In this sense, the project website features a sign-up form in both 'Contact' and 'Open Calls' pages as a call-to-action towards the interested users to join the project's community and keep up with the latest developments.

SUBSCRIBE TO OUR NEWSLETTER

Subscribe

* indicates required

Email Address *

First Name *

Last Name *

Type of organisation *

Please indicate the sector of your job function

Figure 19. Newsletter sing-up form embedded in project website

2.4.4. Networking activities

The project’s expected impacts entail a multitude of efforts, which in many cases are going to be realised via the organisation of diverse events both online and in person format. Hence, the present strategy is positioned closely towards the project’s plans for enhancing the knowledge sharing among the target stakeholders in regards the insights, lessons learnt, best practices and results attained through the project. The organisation of EVOLVE2CARE events, the combination of project events with partners’ own events and the participation/contribution to third-party events are the three major pathways towards attaining knowledge sharing goals.

2.4.4.1. Project events

EVOLVE2CARE has a particular focus on facilitating the sharing of knowledge on the experimentation frameworks and procedures for testing innovations in HealthTech. Hence this, and in accordance with the Grant Agreement of the project, the present strategy is going to work on the delivery of the following project events:

Tailored Training Programs: The project is going to organise two events for training purposes targeted at the Accelup onboarded Living Labs and the applicant Innovators. These two events may take the form of workshops and/or webinars in order to facilitate the participation of **at least 30 Living Labs and 18 innovators**. The training programs’ scope will revolve around validating the project’s main findings on the challenges in transitional care and the potential of HealthTech to address them. The participating innovators, regulators, healthcare providers and Living Lab representatives will validate such findings guided by the program-facilitating project partners. Moreover, these trainings will also serve to strengthen the collaboration framework between these

stakeholders and solidify the envisioned matchmaking process in order to collectively research and test new HealthTech solutions in real-world settings.

Knowledge sharing workshops: Later into the project's mature stages, two more workshops are envisioned. The goal of these workshops will be to showcase the outcomes of the collaborations established via the project's effort (facilitated by the Accelup platform), ensure collective understanding of the innovation ecosystem and commercialization strategies for the engaged target groups, and prompt continuous learning through post-experimentation feedback and knowledge exchange mechanisms. The attendance for these workshops is projected to reach up to **100 Living Lab representatives, 20 RTOs, 20 Multipliers** (accelerators, incubators, tech parks), **10 regulators** and **50 innovators, researchers, SMEs and/or startups** across Europe and beyond.

2.4.4.2. Partners events

Based on the input by the outreach assessment surveys, the project partners have noted that there are a few events held by their own organisations, whose scope/themes can be leveraged for the project's objectives. In light of this, the events below can be taken into account as valuable opportunities for outreach efforts of the project:

AUTH's University Events: Being the largest and one of the oldest Higher Education Public Institutions of Greece, AUTH demonstrates a plethora of outreach events that bring together educational, industrial and societal stakeholders. The School of Medicine, where iMedPhysic Lab, the project coordinator, belongs, organises various events including the AUSoM talks, while it also hosts significant international conferences such as the Association of Medical Schools in Europe (AMSE) Conference and national ones like the Panhellenic Congress of Medical students for Public Health. Such efforts can be leveraged by the project to attain catalysing reach towards its stakeholders' groups.

ENoLL OpenLivingLab Days (OLLD): This annual conference constitutes the flagship event of the organisation. Each year, ENoLL hosts an international gathering of Living Lab professionals, changemakers, shapers, entrepreneurs, and academics. The OLLD conference is a place to develop new ideas and form partnerships. Professionals join to share their thoughts and experiences on the most pressing societal and environmental matters. The conference is co-hosted by ENoLL members, and the location varies yearly. The next version will be held in Andorra, Spain, between 29 September and 2 October 2025.

Health and Wellbeing Living Labs symposium: The 2025 edition is titled "Living Labs in Health and Medicine: Collaborative Innovation for Transforming Care and Wellbeing". The event will aim to place multi-stakeholder collaboration at the heart of innovation, with Living Labs playing a transformative role in addressing Health and Wellbeing

challenges. By assessing the impact and envisioning the future of Living Labs, the conference seeks to drive forward research and innovation in Health and Wellbeing. In addition, the conference will foster discussions on innovative methodologies for stakeholder engagement, ethical considerations, and the challenges of data management in this domain. The event is schedule to take place at Istanbul, Turkey on 13 and 14 May 2025.

2.4.4.3. Third party events

The networking activities are going to expand towards third party events as well. Provided the answers of partners in the outreach capacity assessment, diverse networks are at the disposal of project partners, who have indicated their plans to disseminate the project in workshops, conferences, exhibitions, forums, symposiums, and other types of events. The overarching goal of networking efforts is going to be the awareness raising and the generation of interest among the target groups communities at first, while the pursuit of collaboration ties and active involvement of stakeholders in the project’s implementation is going to be progressively sought.

The following table aggregates a preliminary list of proposed events organised by scientific communities, as these have been put forward by the partners’ assessment surveys. Partners have expressed their plans to examine notable dissemination opportunities in the context of the events below in due time. This mapping of third-party events is set to be periodically updated by VIL, as the WP4 leader, consulting all partners throughout the entire project duration in order to act promptly upon any suitable call to action.

Table 7. Preliminary list of relevant third-party events

Event Title	Topics/Keywords	Location (City, Country, Format)	Date	Target Group(s)
Athens Digital Health Week 2025	Digital health	Athens, Greece Hybrid	27-31 January, 2025	Researchers, innovators, policy makers
ISPIM Connects Cape Town Conference - "Transforming Futures Through Innovation"	HealthTech, Healthcare and Innovation Management	Cape Town, South Africa; In-person	17-19 March 2025	Innovation professionals from academia, industry, consulting, and the public sector

13th EAI International Conference on Wireless Mobile Communication and Healthcare	Healthcare, Industry, 5G Mobile computing	Patras, Greece, Hybrid	29-30 April 2025	Medical Researchers Data Experts, Engineers Health Associations
25th International Conference on Integrated Care	Integrated care	Lisbon, Portugal	14-16 May, 2025	Patients, professionals, researchers, caregivers
Medical Informatics Europe 2025	Medical informatics	Glasgow, Scotland Hybrid	18-21 May 2025	Researchers, innovators
ISPIM Innovation Conference - "Innovation Powered by Nature"	Health and Biotechnology, Healthcare and innovation management	Bergen, Norway Hybrid	15-18 June 2025	Innovation professionals from academia, industry, consulting, and the public sector
19th EAI International Conference on Pervasive Computing Technologies for Healthcare	Pervasive Computing Patient care AI, data and connected systems	Eindhoven, The Netherlands, Hybrid	15 – 17 October 2025	Medical Researchers Data Experts, Engineers Health Associations

Moreover, the project is going to work towards reaching out to sister EU-funded projects and initiatives in order to explore alliances under shared interests and field of activities. Becoming part of a wider network of synergies will promote that EVOLVE2CARE expands its network and facilitates knowledge exchange in larger and targeted pathways. VIL is going to work closely with ENOLL, the T4.3- Clustering with EIT KICs leader, to study the European ecosystem and conduct a list of sister projects, whose scope can potentially lead to clustering activities and collaboration actions (e.g., joint workshops and webinars).

2.4.5. Publications

Project scientific and/or technical peer reviewed publications

The projected scientific papers and technical articles will be submitted for publication in conference proceedings and scientific peer-reviewed journals in Europe and beyond. Conference proceeding papers serve as a valuable mean to introduce colleagues to new

ideas, present the project's work, and refine research questions. Additionally, the project's publications will help in promoting further research activities that may build upon the project's findings. The project aims to pursue the route of Open Access for EVOLVE2CARE publications, making them available in trustworthy repositories. However, this pursuit will be balanced with the project's obligations to protect results, maintain confidentiality, and safeguard personal data.

Based on the information collected through the assessment of partners outreach resources and capacity, a few journals have been pointed out whose scope is considered relevant to the project. This indicative list, presented in the table below, serves as the starting point for a continuous evaluation of publishing opportunities. Similar to the third-party events mapping, VIL is going to update this list too, being in close communication with all partners to leverage the produced knowledge.

Table 8. Indicative list of relevant Journals

Journal Title	Domain(s)	Publisher	Publication rights
Sustainability (ISSN 2071-1050)	Sustainable Impact and Systemic Change via Living Labs	MDPI	Open Access
International Journal of Medical Informatics	Medical Informatics	Elsevier Ireland Ltd	Open Access option
Health Informatics Journal	Health Informatics	Sage Journals Home	Open Access option
International Journal of Integrated Care	Integrated Care	Ubiquity press	Open Access option
BMJ Innovations	Health Innovation	BMJ	Open Access option
Journal of Market Access & Health Policy	Health Policy	MDPI	Open Access
Healthcare	Health Care Sciences and Services Leadership and Management	MDPI	Open Access

Apart from the journals of the above-listed publishing houses, the dissemination of the project is going to explore publishing pathways offered by the supporting, free-of-charge, services managed by the EC:

- [Open Research Europe platform](#): An open access, publishing platform for scientific papers for Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe beneficiaries, including open peer review and article revision.
- [Horizon Results platform](#): A platform for showcasing research results, finding collaboration opportunities and getting inspired by the results of others.

- **Innovation Radar:** An initiative that identifies high-potential innovations, based on a data-driven methodology, and assists EU-funded researchers and innovators in reaching the market with their innovation.

As a general rule, the envisioned scientific and/or technical publications will have to comply with specific requirements coming from EC in regards the acknowledgement of the EU funding. Therefore, authoring partners need to bear in mind that their papers should **always include the following statement:**

- *“This [paper/work/article] is conducted in the context of EVOLVE2CARE project, that has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101158152.”*

In cases where additional disclaimer should be used, the following statement can accompany the funding acknowledgement:

- *“Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”*

Non-peer-reviewed, popularised publications

In addition to the dissemination-oriented publications, the project will work on publications whose role is to communicate the project in short and concise manner. **Press releases and blog posts** are going to be elaborated throughout the project’s progress to address the needs of information sharing and promotion of the project overall.

The preparation of press releases will provide a more formal manner that is channelled towards national and/or European media organisations. EVOLVE2CARE will prepare press releases to raise awareness and communicate information about the project. Press releases will refer to pivotal project events or relevant milestones. Such media material will be published on project’s website, on social media pages and through press contacts of the partner organisations.

Blog posts are going to be curated by VIL, with active consultation from partners as well. Such generalised posts can serve as an easy-to-grasp form of promoting updates about the project in a sustainable frequency. In their majority, blog posts will refer to either EVOLVE2CARE core aspects, important findings and how project’s key results can positively impact contemporary challenges of innovation for the Transitional Care. The content of the blogs will be sourced in the plethora of activities and deliverables that project partners will assume, which means that all partners are going to contribute.

2.4.6. Zenodo community

Zenodo is a general-purpose open repository developed under the European OpenAIRE program and operated by CERN. It allows researchers to deposit research papers, data sets, research software, reports, and any other research related digital materials. It is a strong supporter of open data in all its forms (meaning data that anyone is free to use, reuse, and redistribute) and takes an incentives approach to encourage depositing under an open license.

To that end, the project has set up a [Zenodo community](#) in October 2024 (M1), where all public deliverables, presentations, publications, e-newsletters, policy briefs and/or any other document/material that would be useful and interesting for project's stakeholders will be uploaded, curated, and made freely available under open access status.

2.5. Monitoring and evaluation

2.5.1. Governance

VIL, as the WP4 leader, is responsible for the overall coordination of the dissemination, communication and outreach strategy for the project, which means that it will oversee and be involved with all the efforts that will fall into the scope of the project's promotion. Having the main coordination, VIL is assigned to lead the dissemination and communication activities planning, along with the responsibility to ensure adequate preparations, guidance for implementation in accordance with the preparations and efficient reporting when the activities are completed.

Nevertheless, the responsibilities are not limited to VIL's coordination. That is, **all partners are contractually involved with the dissemination and communication efforts** of the project. Hence, partners share an equal responsibility and right to review the planned activities, provide their feedback to VIL, distribute the workload and collaborate in order to meet the goals of the present strategy.

In light of the above, the roles can be assumed among partners as follows:

- **Coordinator:** VIL, is responsible for overseeing the activities, provide guidance and maintain the monitoring and reporting.
- **Activity Leader(s):** The main partner(s) to have an activity done.
- **Activity Facilitator(s):** The partners to contribute either by providing the information needed, delivering the content and/or helping the outreach efforts.

The present strategy is going to be continuously evaluated in the context of the project’s plenary management telcos, during which the dedicated slot for WP4 status updates is predefined. VIL is going to structure these plenary briefings in three parts:

1. **Status so far:** Recently implemented and completed activities/efforts will be summarised, allowing partners to comment on their progress.
2. **Next steps:** Forthcoming actions that are linked to short and mid-term goals of the strategy, kick-starting a preliminary discussion on how to work them.
3. **Special focus:** An additional part for bringing the partners attention to significant, upcoming and/or pending, and resource-demanding issues that may arise, informing partners about such situations and making sure that consensus is attained on how to tackle them.

Ad hoc meetings by VIL with partners who are assigned with an activity will be also part of the strategy’s governance to afford clarity of goalsetting sufficient guidance, thus strengthening the spirit of team-effort. To this end, a brief template for planning an activity is going to be used by VIL (see Annex). The rationale for using a simple planning template is to distil the most important information and have all partners fully aware and onboard with the process, its purpose and the estimated end-goals in a clear and time-efficient way.

Last but not least, VIL is going to deliver **periodic overview** of the dissemination, communication and outreach efforts status **in each official project management meeting** that is going to be organised by the coordination team and the hosting partners.

2.5.2. Action plan

The present strategy is going to unfold in three distinct phases, as these have been defined in the project’s GA. The implementation of the dissemination, communication and outreach efforts will adhere to the scope of each phase and the projected outcomes will actualise the corresponding measures.

The table below provide a summative view of each phases description and primary measures/actions to be taken

Table 9. Dissemination, communication and outreach stages overview

Stage 1 - Awareness (from October 2024 - M1 to March 2025 - M6)	
Scope of the phase	Measures and actions to be taken
The initial stage revolves around designing the strategy for disseminating and communicating the project. It also includes the refinement of target	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Project website and social media pages set up ✓ Dissemination, communication and outreach strategy delivered

<p>groups and the allocation of appropriate tools for reaching out to each group category.</p> <p>The ground-setting community building activities should take place informing relevant key stakeholders about EVOLVE2CARE scope and objectives. This is directly inked with creating a dedicated community and gathering stakeholder requirements.</p> <p>In this stage, the project should also define the relevant EU policies and strategies which should target to influence. The definition of liaison and interaction mechanisms with relevant projects and initiatives within and beyond EVOLVE2CARE context is also expected in order to identify complementarities, common practices, opportunities for collaboration and jointly organised activities.</p> <p>The first stage is all about ensure maximum contribution by all partners, planning of first events organisation and participation.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Event calendar created ✓ Project introduction flyer and presentation drafted ✓ Preliminary participation to relevant conferences and events presenting EVOLVE2CARE objectives and core foundation, ✓ First newsletter circulated ✓ First project webinar organised ✓ Planning of envisioned project workshops ✓ Liaisons with key relevant initiatives, local and regional media channels commenced ✓ Stakeholder community building kick-started ✓ Co-creation activities for requirements gathering facilitated
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Stage 2 - Community outreach
(from April 2025 - M7 to December 2025 - M14)

Scope of the phase	Measures and actions to be taken
<p>The second stage includes actively reaching out to the main target stakeholders and generating interest in EVOLVE2CARE activities and outputs.</p> <p>The goal is to mobilise and create awareness in the ecosystems around the EVOLVE2CARE and the linked initiatives and stakeholders. Onboard Living Labs and Innovators to the EVOLVE2CARE platform. Moreover, this stage will work on fostering knowledge and best practices exchange around the EVOLVE2CARE concepts.</p> <p>This stage will set a solid foundation for the advanced dissemination and communication activities. In this respect, the project is going to start showcasing policy making and intervention activities. The project will proceed with organisation of stand-alone or joint events, while also focusing on paving the way for impact creation and assessment activities.</p> <p>This stage is going to also put significant efforts towards onboarding Living Labs to the Accelup platform.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Relevant videos, animations and informational materials are crated and promoted via social media channels and the EVOLVE2CARE YouTube channel and website ✓ Newsletters, news items and technical papers are issued ✓ Third party events attended ✓ Project use cases disseminated ✓ AccelUP promotion with dedicated campaigns carried out ✓ Dedicated workshop to present and validate EVOLVE2CARE concept and tools held ✓ Joint sessions and webinars organised ✓ Early project results are shared in Open Access ✓ Impact research webinars realised ✓ Standardisation, policy and impact assessment events sought ✓ Connections with local and regional media leveraged

Stage 3 - Global outreach and sustainability

(from December 2025 - M15 to September 2026 - M24)	
Scope of the phase	Measures and actions to be taken
<p>The final stage will gravitate towards actively engaging and supporting the adoption and deployment of the EVOLVE2CARE concepts technologies and tools offered. In this stage, efforts will put on the promotion of the EVOLVE2CARE results and validation activities. New promotional materials will be developed and distributed, while project results are shared via Open Access. Partners will continue disseminating the project and its results in key events; and tailored marketing activities will be held.</p> <p>This final stage is going to also introduce business exploitation and impact assessment activities. Extended liaisons with key stakeholders and relevant initiatives will be agreed to promote key project results with special campaigns.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Training programmes to key stakeholders (LLs, Innovators). ✓ Promotional materials updated and dedicated promotional activities held ✓ White papers conducted ✓ Newsletters, interviews, videos and further marketing activities carried out. ✓ Joint sessions and webinars organised ✓ Final exploitation and sustainability plan delivered ✓ Final Impact assessment and community activities implemented ✓ Policy recommendations draft and published ✓ Roadmap and guidelines for replication provided Liaison with media channels for broad visibility and awareness landed ✓ Participation to relevant startup events sought

Drawing from the above structure, the roll-out of activities is put forward in a tentative calendar so that an even distribution of efforts and workload can be sustained during the project. The table below aggregates a preliminary allocation of activities throughout the project lifespan. It is essential to annotate, though, that the distribution below is indicative and shall remain subject to revisions and planning with additional activities, as the project moves forward and more detail information about the efforts’ status are available.

Table 10. Tentative calendar for the dissemination, communication and outreach efforts

Stage	Month	Activity	Leader(s)/Facilitator(s)
Stage 1 - Awareness	M1 - OCT 2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project Visual identity • Website & social media pages • Project start press release • Kick-off Meeting news item 	VIL/ALL Partners
	M2 - NOV 2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preliminary promotional items (slides, flyer) • Promotion survey for drivers and barriers in innovation in Transitional Care 	VIL/ALL Partners
	M3 - DEC 2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dissemination, communication and outreach strategy and materials • Preliminary project video • HealthTech Investor Summit 	VIL/ALL Partners

	M4 - JAN 2025	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stakeholders' mapping Project's key info campaign in social media Athens Digital Health Week 2025 	VIL/ALL Partners
	M5 - FEB 2025	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Blog post (D1.1) Blog post (D5.3) Project partners presentation in social media 	VIL/SPLORO VIL/AV VIL/ALL Partners
	M6 - MAR 2025	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Activities reporting First Newsletter ISPIM Connects Cape Town Conference 	VIL/ALL Partners
Stage 2 - Community Outreach	M7 - APR 2025	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Blog post (D1.2) Press release about the Advisory Board 13th EAI International Conference on Wireless Mobile Communication and Healthcare 	VIL/AUTH ENoLL
	M8 - MAY 2025	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Activities reporting Blog post (D1.3) 25th International Conference on Integrated Care Medical Informatics Europe 2025 	VIL/ALL Partners
	M9 - JUN 2025	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Project Newsletter, Press Release (MS1) ISPIM Innovation Conference 	VIL/AUTH ENoLL
	M10 - JUL 2025	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Activities reporting Project video New promotional materials 	VIL/ALL Partners
	M11 - AUG 2025	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Seasonal Greetings 	VIL/ALL Partners
	M12 - SEP 2025	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Activities reporting Press Release and Campaign about Accelup (D2.1 - 2.2 / MS2, MS3) 	VIL/SPLORO VIL/AV VIL/ALL Partners
	M13 - OCT 2025	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 19th EAI International Conference on Pervasive Computing Technologies for Healthcare 	AUTH
	M14 - NOV 2025	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Activities reporting Training webinar (D2.3 - 2.4) Press Release Blog post (D2.3 - 2.4) Project video 	VIL/ALL Partners ENoLL, AV/VIL
Stage 3 - Global outreach and	M15 - DEC 2025	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Seasonal Greetings 	VIL/ALL Partners
	M16 - JAN 2026	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Activities reporting Project video 	VIL/ALL Partners
	M17 - FEB 2026	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Project newsletter New promotional materials 	VIL/ALL Partners

M18 - MAR 2026	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Activities reporting 	VIL/ALL Partners
M19 - APR 2026	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Blog post (D1.5 - 1.6) 	VIL/AUTH
M20 - MAY 2026	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Activities reporting 	VIL/ALL Partners
M21 - JUN 2026	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Project Newsletter 	VIL/ALL Partners
M22 - JUL 2026	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Activities reporting Project video 	VIL/ALL Partners
M23 - AUG 2026	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Press release Blog post (WP3 Ds) 	VIL, ENoLL, AUTH/ALL Partners
M24 - SEP 2026	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Activities reporting Final Newsletter Press release 	VIL/ALL Partners

2.5.3. Reporting and Feedback

Upon the completion of any activity, partners will fill the Dissemination, Communication and Outreach Report Form (see Annex), so that a robust book-keeping of efforts is maintained. The form is stored at a dedicated space in the project’s repository and partners will use it to provide specific information on the type of their activity and a series of simple, yet necessary, details of it.

VIL is going to communicate the reporting form with all project partners in a bi-monthly base in order to collect data about the activities and efforts carried out by each partner. Moreover, when an opportunity for an activity emerges, partners need to notify WP4 leader, VIL, about it, to document such action accordingly and provide any necessary assistance (e.g. reminding guidelines, giving tips for better communication etc.)

2.5.4. Target Indicators

The above procedures are necessary to be grasped by all partners and implemented accordingly, in order to establish a smooth cooperation since the data collected throughout monitoring and reporting of EVOLVE2CARE dissemination, communication and outreach efforts is going to be benchmarked against the measures to maximise impact as they have been predefined in project’s Grant Agreement. The following table includes the core Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) that should be attained by the completion of the project:

Table 11. Dissemination, communication and outreach KPIs according to GA

Tools and Measures	Indicators	Target values
Social Media*	LinkedIn followers	+600
	Facebook followers	+600
	YouTube followers	+150
	Impressions (monthly)	+3000

Website	Monthly unique visitors	+500
	Monthly recurrent visitors	+600
	Monthly pageviews	+1000
Mailing campaigns	Mailing campaigns	10
	Open rate	20%
Events	Major events attended	4
	EC-events attended	2
	EIT KIC events	5
Media	Articles in media	+10
	Press releases	10
Promotional videos	AccelUP Videos	3
	Overall views	+1000

*In light of the actions taken by EC last year, when the Commission opened formal proceedings to assess potential breaches of the Digital Services Act (DSA) by X (former Twitter)⁶ in areas linked to risk management, content moderation, dark patterns, advertising transparency and data access for researchers, the present strategy has opted to not use the platform. The project is dedicated to openly communicating its progress and produced knowledge, under the most accurate and truthful terms. All partners are aligned with the strategy's approach towards adequate communication to the best of their capabilities.

Taking into account this ongoing investigation in conjunction with the feedback on the partners online channels (see Table 3) the present strategy has conclude to not set up an X account but put more efforts into the alternative social media platforms instead. In this sense, the strategy has set a higher target indicator for both Facebook and LinkedIn pages to 600 followers, thus balancing the audience impact in online channels.

The evaluation of the Dissemination Strategy is based on addressing the indicators and the fulfilment of the outcomes that are presented. All partners are responsible to

⁶ "Press corner," *European Commission - European Commission*, Dec. 18, 2023. https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/IP_23_6709

contribute to the efforts to be made in order to successfully reach the planned results. Inner-project communication between partners and VIL and timely reporting are the fundamental aspects to dissemination and communication actions. In addition, communication among EVOLVE2CARE partners for valuable information sharing on opportunities for collaborative dissemination of the project is highly encouraged.

3. Conclusions

The EVOLVE2CARE Dissemination, Communication, and Outreach Strategy, serves as a dynamic and participatory roadmap, reflecting the collaborative efforts of all project partners to maximise the visibility and impact of the project. Through a well-defined approach that balances creativity and structure, the strategy addresses the needs of diverse stakeholders while ensuring alignment with the project's core objectives.

Key achievements include the establishment of a robust visual identity, the deployment of multi-channel communication tools, and the development of targeted promotional campaigns. These efforts have laid a strong foundation for ongoing and future activities, particularly in enhancing stakeholder engagement, fostering knowledge sharing, and promoting the adoption of innovative practices in Transitional Care. The phased implementation ensures adaptability, allowing for continuous improvements based on feedback and evolving project needs.

As EVOLVE2CARE moves forward, the strategy is going to be revised and enhanced, this keeping up with the progress and the needs of project while targeting to pave the way for the sustainability and long-term impact. By focusing on actionable insights, stakeholder collaboration, and alignment with broader European innovation frameworks, the project is going to continuously update the present strategy and maintain a recognisable, positive mark in the field of HealthTech and Transitional Care.

Last but not least, the overview of the strategy's implementation and outcomes is going to be presented in detailed and assessed against its objectives in the consequent deliverable, *D4.4 - Dissemination, Communication and Outreach Strategy and Materials - Final* due at the end of the project, September 2026 (M24).

Annex

Dissemination Reporting Form

Dissemination, communication and outreach reporting form

Partner

Type of the activity

If 'Other' please specify

(Please not apply to any of the types entitled above, please describe the activity)

Status of the activity

Title of activity / slogan

(Please not apply to any of the types entitled above)

Title of the event (if applicable)

Venue (if applicable) **Date**
 _____ _____

Title of the presentation (if applicable)

url of the activity (if applicable)

url of the publication (if applicable)

Type of audience reached below. Please select more than one type ONLY if applicable.
 Please indicate ESTIMATED number of individuals per type of audience (Requested by EC)

Industry/business partners	Innovators	EU Institutions	National authorities	Regional authorities	Local authorities	Civil Society	Citizens	Research communities	Specific and user communities	International organisation (UN body, OECD, etc.)	Other	Investors
Number	Number	Number	Number	Number	Number	Number	Number	Number	Number	Number	Number	Number

Please give a brief explanation of the activity and its objectives with reference to the project's goals (max. 200 characters)

Please copy below any photos or copy relevant links (e.g. to videos, presentation files, announcement screenshots, etc.)

Stakeholders' mapping template

Target audience groups	Stakeholder identification <i>Please provide: i) the title of the organisation; ii) its type, and iii) persons who can contact directly if applicable</i>	Contact information <i>Please provide: i) the official website of the organisation; and ii) the email addresses of persons who can contact</i>	Referring Partner <i>Please indicate who proposes the current stakeholders</i>	Rationale <i>Please indicate the usefulness of engaging these stakeholders</i>
Innovators				
Accelerators and Investors				
Living Labs				
End-users (Care Units, Hospitals, Practitioners)				
End-users (Individuals)				
Policymakers and Regulatory Bodies				
EU Initiatives				

Dissemination, Communication and Outreach activity Plan template

Key questions for planning

Activity
<i>Guide question: What activity do we need to carry out for the project's needs?</i>

 Purpose

Guide question: What is the purpose of the communication activity, why is this activity required?

 Key message(s)

Guide question: What are the main messages we want to convey?

 Content/Format

Guide question: What kind of content, formatting, medium and channels should we use to conduct the communication activity?

Choose from the following options: Face-to-face meeting

 Frequency

Guide question: How often will we have this communication activity?

Choose from the following options: Weekly, Monthly, Quarterly, Annually or Ad Hoc

 Actor(s)

Guide question: Who is responsible to carry out this communication activity?

 Leader – The main partner to have the activity done

 Facilitator(s) – This partner (or partners) to contribute either by providing the information needed, delivering the content and/or helping the outreach efforts

 Target Group(s)

 Audience – The main information receivers

 Outcome(s)

Guide question: What we aim to achieve via this communication activity and once it is completed?
Indicate the final outcome(s) of the communication activity.

Summary of the activity planning

| Outcome(s) |
|--|---|--|--|---|--|---|--|
| | | | | | | | |
| | | | | | | | |